

Planet RDC Program 2.2:

Domain Data Portals (DDP)

Program Guidelines

The purpose of these guidelines is to provide potential project partners with the program strategy and intended outcomes, and clear guidance around expectations for projects.

Program Overview	1
Program Outcomes	2
Project requirements	3
In Scope Activities	3
Out of Scope Activities	4
Process and Timeline	4
Investment and Duration	5
ARDC expectations for the conduct of co-investment projects	6

Revision History

Version	Date	Editor	Summary of changes
0.1	14 Feb 2024	Julia Martin	Draft
0.2	26 Feb 2024	Julia Martin	Feedback from Hamish and Kerry incorporated.
1.0	24 Apr 2024	Julia Martin	Version for publishing

Program Overview

The Planet Research Data Commons aims to improve access to FAIR environmental and climate data held in federated repositories through its [Domain Data Portals program](#) (DDP). This program sits within the Planet RDC Focus Area - FAIR & Integrated Data & Services.

Phase one of the DDP program will target the National Environmental Science Program ([NESP](#)) community. NESP is Australia's longest running environmental research program, into which DCCEEW has invested \$149 million (2020 to 2027). Also in scope is the NCRIS facility Australian Plant Phenomics Facility ([APPF](#)) community.

Both NESP and APPF generate a wealth of data and other outputs from research on the environment, biodiversity and climate. These outputs present a valuable opportunity for Australian researchers, however they are scattered across institutional repositories that lack interoperability. The inconsistency in content, granularity, data quality and governance protocols further complicate the matter. A significant challenge arises for some hubs, due to the absence of metadata, rendering many researchers, and indeed the NESP program leaders, unaware of the data. The inability to find the data also hinders the translation of research into environmental management and decision-making.

The DDP program will deliver flexible but robust discovery and aggregation of datasets across these institutional repositories by developing rich metadata records for every project output and have this metadata discoverable nationally. This will be achieved by leveraging host institutional infrastructure and the ARDC investments in national data and informatics infrastructure, including data publishing services of Research Data Australia (RDA), Research Vocabularies Australia (RVA), persistent identifiers (PIDs), communication, skills uplift and engagement activities. These services will support the consistent adoption of community standards, enabling research outputs that are findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR).

Program Outcomes

The DDP program will deliver flexible but robust discovery and aggregation of NESP and APPF research outputs through nominated institutional repositories. This will be achieved by:

- Each partner will support the end goal of Activity 2.2 which is cohesive domain discovery of all NESP and APPF research outputs in a Domain Portal within Research Data Australia.
- Each portal will contain standardised and interconnected descriptions of research outputs, enhancing discovery and translation of research, and enabling tracking of research impact.

- Undertaking a landscape gap analysis. The analysis will identify the current state of data holdings per partner, and develop a plan to implement domain standards in data, metadata, persistent identifiers and the ability to harvest the metadata into Research Data Australia.
- Leveraging the ARDC investments in national data and informatics infrastructure, including data publishing services of Research Data Australia (RDA), Research Vocabularies Australia (RVA), persistent identifiers (PIDs), communication, skills uplift and engagement activities.
- These services will support the consistent adoption of community standards, enabling research outputs that are findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR).
- The Domain Data Portals program requires a co-design approach between ARDC, APPF and the NESP Research Hubs to develop improved data publishing and discovery mechanisms through the assigning of persistent identifiers in resource metadata.

In Scope Activities

- Landscape analysis of research output holdings and related repository capability to support the program.
- Creation of rich descriptions (metadata) for research outputs, with the inclusion persistent identifiers for :
 - Datasets and collections ([DOI](#))
 - Software ([DOI](#))
 - Services (DOI)
 - Instruments (DOIs)
 - Physical objects, e.g. sample and specimen (DOI)
 - Researchers ([ORCiDs](#))
 - Organisations ([RoRs](#))
 - Investments (DOIs)
 - Programs and projects ([RAiDs](#))
- The harvesting of this metadata into [Research Data Australia](#)

Out of Scope Activities

ARDC cannot invest directly in the following (although other partners may provide these outputs as part of the project):

- Sampling or surveying to fill data gaps
- Research.

Process and Timeline

The Planet RDC is following a community co-design process to deliver its programs.

- 2022 - National consultation and policy analysis identified major national stakeholders and national priorities (see the [Planet RDC Program Description](#)).
- 2024
 - Q1 2024 - Project shaping phase - we will hold meetings with potential delivery partners and stakeholders to identify and select potential solution(s) and finalise the project team(s)
 - Project planning phase, where we will work with identified project partners to develop an investable project plan.
 - Q2 2024 - Projects and ARDC workshops to standardise metadata elements and PIDs
 - Q3 2024- Repository services review across partner networks by project, including PID strategy and harvesting to RDA strategy/agreement with repository partners.
 - Q4 2024 - Deliver metadata and PID requirements to project leads and research partners.
 - Q4 2024 - workshop RDA crosswalk enhancements with ARDC NII Business Unit per repository partner.
 - Q1 2025 - Commence publication of metadata from pilot repositories into RDA, testing domain data portal view.
 - Q2 2025 - Commence publication of all metadata from partner repositories into RDA.
 - Q3 2025 - Develop contingency strategy for partners whose repositories cannot support the metadata/PID requirements.
 - Q4 2025 - transition projects and business processes into BAU service/s.

Investment and Duration

The total ARDC budget for the Domain Data Portals program is \$700 k over 2 years (2024-2025).

The project duration is up to two years, with an expectation that the new pipeline of metadata into Research Data Australia will be maintained on an ongoing basis by the project partners following the formal project phase.

ARDC policy requires a minimum of 1:1 co-investment ratio between ARDC's investment and that of all the other project participants combined. See the [ARDC's Co-investment Guidelines](#) for details.

ARDC expectations for the conduct of co-investment projects

- Project partners will match ARDC co-investment at a 1:1 ratio. Both cash and in-kind co-investment are acceptable. All co-investment must be made in an auditable form (see the [ARDC's Co-investment Guidelines](#) for details).
- Projects must be aligned with the [National PID Strategy](#), [NCRIS 2023 Guidelines](#) and the Principles set out in the [NRI Roadmap](#) (pg 14 pdf, pg 21 doc)
- Projects must have a dedicated project manager with appropriate experience and capacity. Depending on project needs, ARDC may require the naming of a specific Technical Lead and Research Lead
- Projects must have a steering committee (including community members not directly involved in the delivery of the project) with defined Terms of Reference that meets at least quarterly. Depending on project needs, ARDC may require the formation of a user reference group and project management group.
- Projects are required to commit to monthly traffic light reporting and other reporting requirements specified at contracting
- Project plans must include the tracking of desired outcomes, including measuring the uptake of infrastructure by the research community, with clear KPIs that evidence the value to research, government and industry
- Project plans should include user testing of ideas and prototype outputs early and often throughout project delivery
- Most outputs will require ongoing maintenance beyond the life of the project in order to realise the intended benefits. Project plans must include a statement of the minimum ongoing maintenance likely to be required (both duration and resources) and a plan for that maintenance (to be agreed between ARDC and the project partners)
- Project teams are expected to collaborate across the Planet RDC and other ARDC supported projects
- Project teams are expected to attend and contribute to ARDC workshops and events
- Project teams are expected to engage in communication activities to raise awareness of their project and attract a growing user base within the earth and environmental sciences community.